

ASSESSMENT OF THREE EXTRACTION METHODS ON THE CONCENTRATION OF AVAILABLE POTASSIUM (K) IN SOILS FORMED FROM DIVERSE PARENT MATERIALS IN AKWA IBOM STATE

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ABSTRACT

This study was carried out to assess the efficacy of using three extraction methods on the concentration of available potassium on soils formed from Coastal plain sand (CPS) from Obio Akpa in Oruk Anam L.G.A, Sandstone from Mbiakpa Ibakasi in Ini L.G.A and Beach ridge sand from Ikot Ibiok in Eket L.G.A were sampled at two depths (0 – 15 and 15 – 30cm). The soil samples were analyzed in the laboratory using standard procedures. For the

determination of available potassium, three extractants: ammonium acetate (NH_4AOc), hydrochloric acid (HCl), and barium chloride (BaCl_2) were used. The data collected were subjected to statistical analysis using descriptive statistics, and means were compared using Fisher's Least Significant Differences (FLSD) at a 0.05 probability level. The results revealed that the soil was sandy loam in texture, acidic to moderately acidic (4.65 – 5.85), with low nitrogen (0.08 - 0.17) and high available phosphorus (52.95 – 82.45mg/kg). The extracted K differed in concentration and increased in the order: $\text{HCl} < \text{BaCl}_2 < \text{NH}_4\text{AOc}$.

Among the extractants, NH_4AOc extracted more of the available K in the study soils and is therefore recommended for the extraction of available potassium in the studied soils.

Keywords: Potassium Extractants, Soil properties, Parent materials.

INTRODUCTION

Potassium (K) is the third most essential nutrient needed for plant growth. It plays significant roles in the physiological processes of protein synthesis, transportation of water, carbohydrate, photosynthesis, nitrogen utilization and many other functions in plants (Lakudzala, 2013 and Ijah *et al.*, 2024). Soil contains widely variable pools of K that can be potentially mobilized during chemical weathering of minerals (Simonsson *et al.*, 2009). The application of K fertilizer in the soil increases soluble K, with a fraction of it being adsorbed onto the exchange site, lost

through leaching (Ijah *et al.*, 2024) or fixed into non-exchangeable forms. However, the availability of potassium in agricultural soil is of great importance and the concentration of potassium in the soil is an important parameter that is used for fertilizer recommendation (Romheld, 2010). According to Kovacevic (2005). Low content of potassium in the soil limits the yield of agricultural crops. Understanding of soil potassium dynamics is essential for sustainable crop production and bioavailability of potassium depends on forms and distribution within the soil profile (Butt, 2017). Potassium distribution

in the soil environment differs from soil type because of differences in soil minerals, affecting the response to (SS) from G.M.riakpani Area (In G.A) L.Sand and Beach ridge sand (BRS) from Ikot Ibiok in Eket L.G.A of Akwa Ibom State (Figure1). The State is located between

latitudes 4°2' and 5°33' N and Longitudes

of crop K requirements (Samadi, 2006;

Krauss, 2003), while in other countries the K saturation index (%) is used for the

assessment of soil K status (Mutscher, April – October) and is characterized by

1995). However, research has shown that

the mean annual rainfall that varies from

solution and exchangeable K are

about 2,000 mm in the northern parts to

about 4,000 mm along the coastline and a

shorter dry season that spans between

leaching. Bansal *et al.* (2002) showed that

exchangeable K at the year will be used as the

basis for evaluating K availability under

intensive cropping, as those soils

considered sufficient in exchangeable K

were not able to maintain that condition for

long under intensive cropping with high-

yielding varieties. Thus, it is considered

important to study methods of available K

extraction for agricultural soil.

The greatest challenge in the analysis of soil

is to choose extractants which will be able to

extract as many elements as possible and

that are acceptable for a great range of soils

with different characteristics (Jones, 1998).

Different methods are used as a standard in

different countries to extract varying

amounts of K in soil fractions. The choice of

a standard soil test is the result of the

suitability of the extractant for the majority

of soils in that particular region. This study,

however, focuses on the assessment of three

extraction methods on the concentration of

available potassium (K) on soil derived

from different parent materials.

(Bremner, 1996). Available phosphorus (P)

was extracted by the Bray-1 method (Bray

and Kurtz, 1945) and P in solution was

determined colourimetrically using the

ascorbic acid method (Murphy and Riley,

1962). Electrical conductivity was

measured in 1:2.5 soil/water suspensions

725' and 825°E and has the tropical monsoon climate with a longer wet season

November and March. Its daily temperature

°C and 33C respectively.

Soil Sampling and analyses

A total of fifty four (54) soil samples were

obtained at 0-15cm and 15-30cm depth

from three different parent materials and

used for the study. The soil samples were

air-dried, crushed and sieved using a 2mm

mesh sieve. Soil analysis was carried using

standard laboratory procedures for the

determination of soil physical, chemical

properties and for the extraction of

available potassium. Particle size

distribution was determined by the

hydrometer method (Gee and Or,

2002). Soil pH was determined in 1:2.5 soil:

water ratio with a pH meter. Organic carbon

was determined by the dichromate wet

oxidation Method (Nelson and Sommers,

1996). Total nitrogen (N) was determined by

the micro-Kjeldahl digestion procedure

from different parent materials.

(Bremner, 1996). Available phosphorus (P)

was extracted by the Bray-1 method (Bray

and Kurtz, 1945) and P in solution was

determined colourimetrically using the

ascorbic acid method (Murphy and Riley,

1962). Electrical conductivity was

measured in 1:2.5 soil/water suspensions

using an electrical conductivity meter. Exchangeable bases (Ca^{2+} , Mg^{2+} , K^+ and Na^+) were extracted with 1N NH_4OAc . The Ca^{2+} , Mg^{2+} in the extract was determined using atomic absorption spectrophotometer (AAS), while K and Na were determined by flame photometry. Exchangeable acidity was determined by titrimetric method with standard NaOH. The three chemical extractants used for the extraction of

available K in soils formed from the three parent materials were: Ammonium acetate (NH_4OAc), hydrochloric acid (HCl), and barium chloride (BaCl_2). Effective cation exchange capacity (ECEC) was calculated as the sum of exchangeable bases and exchangeable acidity. Base saturation was calculated by dividing the sum of exchangeable bases by ECEC and multiplying by 100.

Key: = Sampling points

Fig. 1: Map of Akwa Ibom State showing the sampling points

Statistical Analysis The data collected were subjected to statistical analysis using descriptive statistics and means were compared using Fisher's Least Significant different (FLSD) at 0.05% probability level (Wahua, 1999).

RESULTS AND DISCUSSION

The Physico-Chemical Properties of the Soils formed from different parent materials

The physico-chemical properties of the soils formed from the different parent materials are presented in Table 1. The particle size analysis shows that, sand content ranged from 71.31% (BRS) to 74.30 % (SS). The interaction between depth and parent materials shows that sand content was high in BRS at 0-15cm depth (73.80%) while SS had the highest sand content at 15-30cm depth (75.80 %). The high sand content in these soils may have resulted from the lithology of parent materials of the area and leaching due to high rainfall. Similar findings were reported by (Ijah et al., 2021 and Ijah et al., 2024) on soils formed from different parent material in Akwa Ibom State. Silt content ranged from 7.00 % in SS to 10.00 % in BRS, respectively. The interaction effect between depth and parent materials shows that, soils formed from BRS had the highest silt (Brady and Weil, 1999) in all the parent

materials. Generally, exchangeable calcium was high (10.00%) and exchangeable magnesium was low (1.00%) in all the parent materials. The low exchangeable K could be due to K fixation. These results are in consonance with the report of (Ijah et al., 2024) on soils supporting rubber plantation in Akwa Ibom State. The order of abundance of the exchangeable cations was Ca > Mg > K > Na. Exchangeable acidity ranged from 1.48cmol/kg in BRS to 1.96cmol/kg in SS.

in the soil. The textural class of the study areas was sandy loam. The pH of the soil

was acidic to moderately acidic with values ranging from 4.65 in SS and 5.85 BRS. This may be due to coarse texture of these soils but however complicated with the high rainfall intensity of the area. This corroborated with the work of Ijah et al., 2021; Ijah et al., 2024 and Enwezor (1981) who noted that most soils become acidic due to intensive leaching. Total nitrogen content in the soils ranged from 0.12 % in BRS to 0.13% in CPS and was generally low irrespective of the depth and parent materials. This finding is in consonant with the report of (Ijah et al., 2024) who reported that tropical soils are characterized with low nitrogen. Organic matter content was moderate ranging between 2.20% in SS and 2.67 % in CPS. The interaction effect shows that organic matter ranged from 2.73 % in SS to 3.41 % CPS at 0-15cm depth. At 15-30 cm depth, organic matter ranged from 1.61 % in BRS to 1.93 % CPS. The high level of organic matter in the top soil than in the sub soil indicates the presence of surface residues and prolific root growth hence microbial populations rapidly decomposes these organic residues and then contribute to the organic matter availability in the soil. Available Phosphorus in the soils ranged from 60.45 mg/kg in SS to 76.15 mg/kg in CPS. It was high above the critical values of 12-15 mg/kg proposed for most crops

in all the parent materials. Generally, silt content at 0-15cm depth was high (73.80%) in BRS and 75.80% in SS at 15-30cm depth. The interaction effect between depth and parent materials shows that, soils formed from BRS had the highest silt (Brady and Weil, 1999) in all the parent materials. Generally, exchangeable calcium was high (10.00%) and exchangeable magnesium was low (1.00%) in all the parent materials. The low exchangeable K could be due to K fixation. These results are in consonance with the report of (Ijah et al., 2024) on soils supporting rubber plantation in Akwa Ibom State. The order of abundance of the exchangeable cations was Ca > Mg > K > Na. Exchangeable acidity ranged from 1.48cmol/kg in BRS to 1.96cmol/kg in SS.

Effective cation exchange capacity ranged from 6.62 cmol/kg in SS to 8.15 cmol/kg in BRS. Base saturation was high in all the soils ranging from 70.40 % in CPS to 81.52 % in BRS. The interaction effect shows that BRS had the highest base saturation of 85.83 % and 77.20 % at 0-15 cm and 15-30 cm depth. The nutrient content available in these soils indicates that the soil is fertile and productive.

Table 1: The Physico-Chemical Properties of the Soils formed from different parent materials

Parent materials	Sand (%)	Silt (%)	Clay (%)	pH	TN (%)	OC (%)	OM (%)	Av.P (mg/kg)	Ca (cmol/kg)	Mg (cmol/kg)	K (cmol/kg)	Na (cmol/kg)
BRS	73.30	10.00	16	5.50	0.12	1.31	2.26	52.95	3.10	1.80	0.17	0.09
CPS	71.31	10.00	20	4.77	0.13	1.55	2.67	76.15	3.35	1.60	0.25	0.15
SS	74.30	7.00	64	4.65	0.12	1.28	2.20	60.45	3.65	1.25	0.17	0.08
(P<0.05)	3.53	3.252	95.2	0.205	0.021	0.114	0.199	0.414	1.935	0.314	0.021	0.006
Depth												
0-15cm	72.81	10.67	16	5.11	0.16	1.752	3.02	74.76	3.00	1.67	0.18	0.09
15-30cm	73.13	7.33	51	4.83	0.09	1.010	1.74	62.26	3.73	1.43	0.21	0.12
(P<0.05)	3.538	2.655	77.7	0.168	0.017	0.093	0.163	0.338	1.580	0.257	0.017	0.005
Depth X Parent material												
BRS (0-15cm)	73.80	12.00	13	5.85	0.16	1.69	2.92	60.40	2.50	2.20	0.19	0.12
CPS (0-15cm)	71.83	10.00	17	4.85	0.17	1.98	3.41	81.45	2.80	1.40	0.16	0.06
SS (0-15cm)	72.80	10.00	17	4.65	0.15	1.58	2.73	82.45	3.70	1.40	0.18	0.09
BRS (15-30cm)	72.80	8.00	19	5.15	0.08	0.93	1.61	45.50	3.70	1.40	0.16	0.06
CPS (15-30cm)	70.80	10.00	23	4.70	0.09	1.12	1.93	70.85	3.90	1.80	0.34	0.24
SS (15-30cm)	75.80	4.00	111	4.65	0.10	0.97	1.67	70.45	3.60	1.10	0.15	0.07
(P<0.05)	5.003	4.598	134.7	0.291	0.029	0.161	0.282	0.586	2.737	0.445	0.030	0.009

EC = Electrical conductivity, AV. P= Available phosphorus, Ca = Exchangeable calcium, Mg = Exchangeable Magnesium, K= Exchangeable potassium, Na= Exchangeable sodium, Ea=Exchangeable acidity, ECEC=Effective cation exchange capacity, BS = Base saturation, CPS= Coastalplainsand, BRS= Beach ridgesand, SS =Sandstone

Effects of Extractants on Available K

Table 2 shows the efficiency of the different extraction methods on available K. Among the extractants studied, NH₄AOc extracted more of available K (0.25 mg/kg) in CPS. BaCl₂ extracted the highest available K in CPS (0.21 mg/kg) and SS (0.21mg/kg) respectively, while the lowest of extractable available K was in SS (0.17 mg/kg) with HCl. At 0-15 cm depth, NH₄AO_c extracted

the highest concentration of available K at (0.24 mg/kg) and (0.19 mg/kg) at 15-30 cm,

BaCl₂extracted (0.18 mg/kg) at 0 – 15cm and (0.22mg/kg) at 15 – 30 cm depth and HCl (0.16 mg/kg) at 0 – 15cm and (0.14 mg/kg) at 15 – 30cm depth. The interaction effect between depth and parent materials at 0-15cm depth shows that, NH₄AO_c extracted the highest concentration of K in

CPS (0.24 mg/kg), BaCl₂extracted more of available K in BRS (0.19) CPS and HCl

(0.17 mg/kg) in SS. At 15-30 cm depth, the interaction effect shows NH_4AOc extracted the highest concentration of available K (0.33 mg/kg) in CPS, BaCl_2 (0.18 mg/kg) in CPS while HCl extracted (0.17 mg/kg) of available K in SS. Generally, NH_4AOc extracted more of available K among the extractants in the different parent materials. The order of increased were: $\text{HCl} < \text{BaCl}_2 < \text{NH}_4\text{AOc}$. The result is in line with the report of Ibia *et al.*, (2024) on soils developed from different parent materials in Akwa Ibom State.

Table 2: Effect of extractants on available K

Parent material	NH_4AOc	BaCl_2	HCl
BRS	0.20 0.25	0.20	0.15
CPS	0.19	0.21	0.13
SS	0.0048	0.21	0.17
P(<0.05)		0.0046	0.038
Depth			
0-15	0.24	0.18	0.16
15-30	0.19	0.22	0.14
P(<0.05)	0.0040	0.0019	0.0031
Depth X Parent Material			
BRS(0-15cm)	0.20	0.19	0.16
CPS (0-15cm)	0.24	0.16	0.15
SS (0-15cm)	0.21	0.18	0.17
BRS (15-30cm)	0.19	0.16	0.14
CPS (15-30cm)	0.33	0.18	0.11
SS (15-30cm)	0.20	0.16	0.17
P(<0.05)	0.0068	0.0034	0.0054

NH_4AOc = Ammonium Acetate, BaCl_2 = Barium Chloride, HCl = Hydrochloric Acid

CPS = Coastal plain sand, BRS = Beach ridge sand, SS = Sandstone

Relationship between the different extraction methods and soil physico-chemical properties at 0-15cm depth
 Table 3 shows the correlation relationship between the different extraction methods and soil physico-chemical properties at 0-15cm depth. Available P, although not significant correlate negatively at (r=-0.724, -0.013) with NH₄Aoc and HCl, positively at (r=0.588) with BaCl₂. Organic matter shows a positive and strong significant (P < 0.05) relationship between

(r= 0.887*) with BaCl₂ and a negative relationship (r=-0.823*, -0.879*) with NH₄Aoc and HCl. Potassium shows a positive and significant (p<0.05) relationship (r= 0.998*) with NH₄Aoc and correlates negatively at (p<0.05) (r=-0.960*) with BaCl₂ although not significantly correlate (r=0.612) with HCl. Sodium correlate positively (r= 0.982*) with NH₄Aoc, and negatively (r= -0.944*) with BaCl₂.

Table 3: Relationship between the different extraction methods and soil physico-chemical properties at 0-15cm depth

	NH ₄ Aoc	BaCl ₂	HCl	Sand	Silt	Clay	pH	Av.P	TN	OC	OM	Ca	Mg	K	Na	EA	ECEC	Bs
NH ₄ Aoc	1																	
BaCl ₂	-0.960**	1																
HCl	0.645	-0.644	1															
Sand	0.826*	-0.680	0.532	1														
Silt	0.390	-0.393	-0.216	0.461	1													
Clay	-0.651	0.501	-0.104	-0.787	-0.768	1												
pH	0.634	-0.482	-0.078	0.666	0.664	-0.913*	1											
Av.P	-0.724	0.588	-0.013	-0.698	-0.630	0.886*	-	1										
TN	-0.509	0.669	-0.409	0.014	0.158	-0.221	0.045	0.091	1									
OC	-0.832*	0.894*	-0.882*	-0.592	-0.057	0.196	-0.099	0.221	0.673	1								
OM	-0.823*	0.887*	-0.879*	-0.587	-0.046	0.178	-0.084	0.206	0.676	1.000**	1							
Ca	-0.113	-0.114	0.130	-0.181	0.188	0.351	-0.551	0.942**	0.133	-0.045	-0.029	1						
Mg	0.615	-0.596	-0.198	0.472	0.768	-0.707	0.854*	-0.878*	-0.276	-0.186	-0.178	0.691	1					
K	0.998*	-0.960*	0.612	0.807	0.404	-0.660	0.660	-0.749	-0.522	-0.811	-0.801	0.599	0.648	1				
Na	0.982*	-0.944**	0.535	0.808	0.530	-0.746	0.726	-0.799	-0.448	-0.748	-0.735	0.644	0.714	0.988	1			
EA	-0.715	0.641	0.048	-0.593	-0.709	0.831*	-	0.971**	0.220	0.241	0.227	-0.848*	-0.956**	-	-0.809	1		
ECEC	0.605	-0.423	-0.071	0.656	0.532	-0.863	0.951**	-	0.058	-0.066	-0.051	0.987*	0.789	0.629	0.676	-0.907*	1	
Bs	0.674	-0.567	-0.089	0.612	0.696	-0.863*	0.985**	-	-0.114	-0.165	-0.150	0.902*	0.932**	0.704	0.768	-0.992**	0.950**	1

Ec = Electrical conductivity, AV. P= Available phosphorus, Ca = Exchangeable calcium, Mg = Exchangeable Magnesium, K= Exchangeable potassium, Na= Exchangeable sodium, EA=Exchangeable acidity, ECEC=Effective cation exchange capacity, BS = Base saturation; NH₄Aoc = Ammonium Acetate, BaCl₂ = Barium Chloride, HCl = Hydrochloric Acid; CPS = Coastal plain sand, BRS = Beach ridge sand, SS = Sandstone

Relationship between the different extraction methods and soil physico-chemical properties at 15-30 cm depth

The correlation relationship between the different extraction methods and soil physico-chemical properties at 15-30 cm depth is presented in Table 4. Silt content correlate positively (r=0.662) with NH₄Aoc and negatively (r=-0.887*, -0.867*) with BaCl₂ and HCl. Available P although not significant correlate negatively at (r=-0.120, -0.065) with BaCl₂,

HCl and positively at (r=0.549) with NH₄Aoc. Magnesium correlate negatively at (r=-0.855*) with HCl. Available Potassium correlate positively at (r=0.990**) with NH₄Aoc and negatively (r=-0.922**, -0.898*) with BaCl₂ and HCl. Sodium correlate positively and significantly (p<0.05) at (r=1.000*) with NH₄Aoc and negatively at (r=-0.877*, -0.859*) with BaCl₂ and HCl. Effective cation exchange capacity (ECEC) had a negative and significant (p<0.05) relationship (r=-0.825*) with HCl.

Conclusion and Recommendation The result of this work has shown that, NH_4OAc extracted more of available K in soils formed from three parent materials. The efficiency of the different extraction methods on available K increased in the order of $\text{HCl} < \text{BaCl}_2 < \text{NH}_4\text{OAc}$. Therefore, NH_4OAc is suitable and more efficient extractant for extraction of available potassium in soil formed from coastal plain sand, beach ridge sand and sandstone soils in Akwa Ibom State and is therefore recommended.

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